

Construction of 3D Networked Epoxy Composite Using RGO and BPEI Coated Epoxy Microspheres for High Thermal Conductivity Application

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INTRODUCTION

Limitations of Conventional Thermally Conductive Polymer Nanocomposites

Disadvantages

Low thermal conductivity of only 0.2 W/mK

Simple approach for enhancing thermal conductivity

Integration of fillers into the polymer matrix

Limitations

- Only a few W/mK along out-of-plane direction
- Alignment primarily along in-plane direction
- Tendency to aggregate by a large specific area

This Study: Thermal Pathways via Segregated RGO

EXPERIMENT

Preparation of Epoxy Microspheres Coated with RGO and BPEI via LBL Method

Fabrication of Epoxy Composite Reinforced with EM-(RGO/BPEI)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological Studies of EM-(RGO/BPEI) and EP/EM-(RGO/BPEI)

- Compared to EM with a smooth surface, EM-(RGO/BPEI)1 showed **increased surface roughness** due to the formation of **homogeneous RGO/BPEI coating**.
- This structure facilitated the development of **continuous thermal conduction pathways** by enabling **interparticle connections** between coated microspheres.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of GO Reduction by Using BPEI

- Oxygen-containing groups were effectively removed and the conjugated structure was restored, confirming the **successful chemical reduction of GO by BPEI**.

Confirmation of EM-(RGO/BPEI) with Various RGO/BPEI Bilayers

- Uniform and controllable RGO/BPEI coating was successfully achieved on the EM as the **number of deposition cycles increased**.

Out-of-Plane Thermal Conductivity as a Function of EM-(RGO/BPEI)1 Content

- The thermal conductivity increased with higher EM-(RGO/BPEI)1 content up to 10 wt% as the greater number of coated EM promoted **more frequent contact points** and resulted in **more effective heat transfer**.

Out-of-Plane Thermal Conductivity as a Function of RGO/BPEI Bilayer Number

- Increasing the number of RGO/BPEI bilayers on EM enhanced out-of-plane thermal conductivity by **increasing the network density** and **improving the connectivity of thermally conductive domains** through a reinforced bridging effect.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visualization on Thermal Properties of EP/EM-(RGO/BPEI)

- The incorporation of EM-(RGO/BPEI) into the epoxy **accelerated heat propagation** through the thickness, as evidenced by **faster surface temperature rise** and **more rapid thermal response** under isothermal heating conditions.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of EP/EM-(RGO/BPEI)

- EP/EM-(RGO/BPEI)5 showed a higher storage modulus and T_g, which reflected **restricted chain mobility** and **increased structural integrity** of the composite.

CONCLUSION

- This study demonstrated a scalable approach to enhance the out-of-plane thermal conductivity of epoxy composites by **constructing 3D conductive networks using epoxy microspheres uniformly coated with RGO/BPEI bilayers** through a LBL assembly process.
- The incorporation of **EM-(RGO/BPEI)5** resulted in a composite with an out-of-plane thermal conductivity of **1.22 W/mK**, corresponding to a **665% enhancement** compared to neat epoxy, offering a structurally controllable and novel design framework with **fundamental potential for high thermal conductivity applications**.

Acknowledgement

- This research was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by Ministry of Science and ICT (2022M3H4A1A04076372)